

Staff Survey

Assessing active learning in an architectural design studio course (staff version)

1. 1. What is your title in " Interior design (1) " studio course?

Mark only one oval.

- Lecturer
- Teaching Assistant

2. 2. As studio course staff member, which studio type did you experience during the pandemic phase (COVID 19)?

Mark only one oval.

- Traditional design studio (in campus/ a physical one-to-one studio)
- Online design studio
- Hybrid/Blended design studio (a mix of traditional and online studios)
- VR studio (Virtual rooms/metaverse)
- Other: _____

3. 3. In comparison with the chosen studio type, based on your opinion, which studio setting was the most efficient in the quality of teaching and learning?

Mark only one oval.

- Traditional design studio
- Online design studio
- Hybrid/Blended design studio
- VR studio
- Other: _____

4. 4. In your interior design (1) studio course, which project do you find more effective in the quality of teaching and learning?

Mark only one oval.

- The individual project
- The collaborative project
- Both
- None of the above

5. 5. During the **INDIVIDUAL** project, which of the **learning by doing** criteria was achieved from your point of view? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- Experiential learning (site visits and observation)
- Inquiry based learning (fixing the project problem through the student's design)
- Collaborative learning (brainstorming with your peers)
- Design-Build programs (Building a 1-1 model by hand or in virtual rooms)

6. 6. During the **COLLABORATIVE** project, which of the **learning by doing** criteria was achieved from your point of view? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- Experiential learning (site visits and observation)
- Inquiry based learning (fixing the project problem through the student's design)
- Collaborative learning (brainstorming with your peers)
- Design-Build programs (Building a 1-1 model by hand or in virtual rooms)

7. 7. As a staff member, what did the **COLLABORATIVE** project experience mainly achieve from the following points? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- Encouraging diverse opinions and interaction
- Encouraging collaborating with other fields (structure engineers, carpenters..etc)
- Gaining new fixation and building skills

8. 8. **Potential learning** prepares students for their professional careers, which project encouraged potential learning in your opinion?

Mark only one oval.

- The individual project
- The collaborative project
- Both
- None of the above

9. 9. Based on your previous answer, how was the **potential learning** achieved? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- Through gaining new business and management skills
- Through professional guidance (professors, Drs, TAs or talks)
- Through offering new competition opportunities
- Other: _____

10. 10. There are several **technological interventions** in studio courses, regarding the taught course, which criteria was needed the most for the quality of teaching and learning? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- An up-to-date staff members
- Incorporating 3D fabrication (with various scales) into the course
- Providing access to a library of digital models
- Providing interactive virtual rooms for students (metaverse)
- Other: _____

11. 11. Based on the previous question, which project achieved the chosen **technological interventions**?

Mark only one oval.

- The individual project
- The collaborative project
- Both
- None of the above

12. 12. An effective teaching and learning process focuses on the design process instead of the final outcome, was this **process-focused** approach achieved?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, in the individual project only
- Yes, in the collaborative project only
- Yes, in both projects
- No, it wasn't achieved

13. 13. Based on your previous answer, which criteria emphasize your **process-focused** answer? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- Critical thinking was encouraged
- Collaboration and interaction were supported
- Workshops and hands-on (building 1-1 or different scales-learning by doing) experience was supported
- Other: _____

14. 14. **Reflective learning** include 4 modes/phases respectively (habitual, understanding, reflection and critical reflection) to improve the student's learning skills, which phase did the majority of students reach in their **INDIVIDUAL** project?

Mark only one oval.

- Habitual phase (receiving new materials/data without understanding)
- Understanding phase (understanding the idea/data received by the staff as facts and theories without an actual application)
- Reflection phase (Fully understand the data and offer useful applications)
- Critical reflection (achieving all the previous points plus providing your own opinion and criticism)

15. 15. **Reflective learning** include 4 modes/phases respectively (habitual, understanding, reflection and critical reflection) to improve the student's learning skills, which phase did the majority of students reach in their **COLLABORATIVE** project?

Mark only one oval.

- Habitual phase (receiving new materials/data without understanding)
- Understanding phase (understanding the idea/data received by the staff as facts and theories without an actual application)
- Reflection phase (Fully understand the data and offer useful applications)
- Critical reflection (achieving all the previous points plus providing your own opinion and criticism)

16. 16. Regarding the teaching and learning experience, how much are you satisfied with the quality of education given during the **INDIVIDUAL PROJECT**?

Mark only one oval.

Absolutely Dissatisfied

1

2

3

4

5

Absolutely Satisfied

17. 17. Regarding the teaching and learning experience, how much are you satisfied with the quality of education given during the **COLLABORATIVE** project?

Mark only one oval.

Absolutely Dissatisfied

1

2

3

4

5

Absolutely Satisfied

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